

Health-Related Quality of Life among Patients with Multiple Sclerosis

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Abstract

Background: MS is a relatively common neurological disease in Saudi Arabia had been increased in prevalence. MS is the most common disease that can cause neurologic disability in patients. Thus, it demands concern knowing the impact of MS on health-related quality of life, disease's progress in those patients can impact the quality of life, so it is important to assess the HRQOL. **Methods:** This study aimed to determine the impact of multiple sclerosis on health-related quality of life (HRQOL) among patients in Saudi Arabia. A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in Prince Sultan Military Medical City in Riyadh, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia from April 2nd, 2023, to May 15th, 2023. The tool used in the collection of data was divided into two parts. Part I included two sections socio-demographic data and illness information. Part II was related to the HRQOL questionnaire (MSQOL-54). The sample included in the study was 300 MS patients. **Result:** This study evaluated 173 females (57.7%) and 127 males (42.3%). Less than half of them (44%) belonged to the age group 25-34 years, and 11% of them were categorized as belonging to the age group of over 44 years. 65% of studied MS patients showed RRMS, while 49 (16.3%) had secondary and primary PMS for both, and only 7 (2.3%) for Progressive-relapsing MS. average score for the studied MS patient PHC, MHC, and overall quality of life were 56.43 ± 17.65 , 56.88 ± 22.0 , and 69.69 ± 18.14 , respectively. **Conclusion and recommendation:** In conclusion, the results of this study provide evidence of a strong interaction between the disease and the physical and mental categories of HRQOL in patients with MS. Also, those patients suffering from impairments in their QOL. Furthermore, health-related quality of life was significantly affected by socio-demographic factors including gender, age, marital status, and employment status, as well as by illness information such as disease duration, number of relapses, and route of medication. Also, this study showed that HRQOL in PwMS is not related to education level and subtype of MS. It recommended conducting health education sessions for patients in disease, treatment, and complication. Also, recommended providing comprehensive care in regular assessment of HRQOL.

Introduction

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a relatively common neurological illness that affects 2.8 million individuals worldwide [1]. The estimated incidence rate of MS worldwide is about 35.9 in every 100 000 population. Its incidence rate continues to rise annually [2]. Nationally, the prevalence of multiple sclerosis in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is increasing, it is estimated to

be 40.4/100000 total population [3]. Multiple sclerosis is an inflammatory and demyelinating disease that is autoimmune-mediated. It attacks the myelinated axons found in the central nervous system, which damages the myelin and the axon causing severe physical disability within 20 to 25 years in approximately 30 percent of multiple sclerosis patients [4]. Therefore, most patients are diagnosed during their 20s until their

More Information

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40s of age, although multiple sclerosis can be developed regardless of age. Research showed it is two to three times more likely among women than men [5]. There are a variety of definitions or models of health-related quality of life (HRQOL), which incorporate four major dimensions: physical, mental, social, and functional health [6]. HRQOL is a subjective and multidimensional concept that allows for the evaluation of the impact of disease or pharmacological and non-pharmacological treatment on these four dimensions and well-being. Identification of life purpose and personal development, particularly in light of a diagnosis of a progressive, chronic illness, provides a much more complete picture of an individual's well-being and is intricately intertwined with HRQOL [6]. The lifelong nature of MS requires consistent attention from healthcare-related professionals, especially for advanced diseases. However, the health-related quality of life among those patients is important to be assessed because the disease's progress can impact the quality of life. As such, the nurse's role is crucial, because nursing care is essential in achieving the most optimal health outcomes for MS patients. Lastly, MS disease can affect the QOL through several factors, such as physical, psychological, and occupational. Despite the importance of this aspect, there is a lack of studies that explore the impact of MS patients on health-related quality of life in Saudi Arabia. The aim of this study led to the following objectives:

- To assess the physical, psychological, and occupational factors that contribute to HRQOL among multiple sclerosis patients in Saudi Arabia.
- To examine the relationship between the severity of multiple sclerosis and HRQOL among patients with MS in Saudi Arabia.

Literature Review

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a chronic inflammatory disease of the central nervous system [6]. MS is one of the most common neurological disorders that causes disability among young adults. It is a chronic, progressive, inflammatory, and demyelinating disease of the central nervous system that has increased incidence and prevalence worldwide [7].

Pathophysiology

The exact etiology of MS is still debated today, as no specific etiology could be pinpointed as the cause of the chronic inflammation and demyelination of nerves of the central nervous system. The pathophysiology is based on two main processes, inflammation, and neurodegeneration, leading to the affection of both motor and sensory aspects of a person, ultimately affecting a patient's perceived quality of life [2].

Multiple Sclerosis

Figure 1: Comparing between Health and Affected Neuron

Risk Factors

Since the cause of multiple sclerosis disease remains inconclusive, it is crucial to know and understand the risk factors involved in the development of the disease. For example, some viral infections increase the risk of developing multiple sclerosis (i.e., Epstein-Barr virus). Genetics are also a risk factor since the lifetime risk of developing multiple sclerosis is about 3 percent if a parent or a sibling has been diagnosed. Also, low vitamin D or sun exposure, air pollution, and organic solvent exposure (i.e., benzene) are considered environmental factors that might cause the disease. Smoking and increased weight can be added to the list of risk factors [8].

Subtypes of MS

Multiple sclerosis is classified into four subtypes: relapsing-remitting MS (RRMS), primary progressive MS (PPMS), secondary progressive MS (SPMS), and progressive relapsing MS (PRMS). The most frequent subtype (about 87%) is RRMS, which is distinguished by unpredictable acute attacks followed by periods of remission [4] (figure 2).

Clinical Manifestation and Complications

The typical manifestation of the disease varies and depends on which area of the central nervous system is affected. Non-specific manifestation of MS includes loss of motor and sensory function, bowel and bladder dysfunction, sexual dysfunction, chronic fatigue, easy fatigability, blindness due to optic neuritis, diplopia, loss of sense of balance, cognitive impairment, clouding of thoughts and emotional changes [2].

Figure 2: Subtypes of MS

[9] reported multiple sclerosis is known to subject patients to a range of symptoms such as muscle weakness in the extremities, vertigo, ataxia, spasticity, and visual impairment. Apart from the notable physical manifestations, individuals may also encounter disruptions in their cognitive abilities [10]. According to [11] individuals may encounter psychological ramifications such as malaise, fatigue, anxiety, depression, low self-esteem, and challenges in both sleeping and concentration. The aforementioned symptoms have a significant impact on an individual's capacity to perform routine tasks, resulting in a consequent disturbance in their education, family relationships, job opportunities, and daily routines. Consequently, a potential decrease in quality of life may ensue [12]. These symptoms can disrupt the patient's life, affecting the overall quality of life. QoL becomes a central focus for patients and their disease management. While rarely fatal, and may cause severe complications in higher stages. Beyond the physiological or physical manifestations, with a special focus on mental health, the mental burden requires serious consideration due to its spillover impact on the physical aspect of a patient and the importance of stable mental capacity regarding QoL. Due to the

progression of MS with age, it becomes necessary to determine how the QoL changes and is impacted by MS [13]. The progression of the disease may result in decubitus ulcers, osteoporosis, urinary tract infections, insomnia, obesity, alterations in work and family life, and psychosocial issues [14]. The clinical presentation of multiple sclerosis is varied and can range from asymptomatic to debilitating. The multifaceted impact of multiple sclerosis (MS) on the lives of those affected poses a challenge in predicting its extent. This condition substantially impacts individuals' autonomy and ability to engage in family and social settings, thereby affecting their overall QoL [15].

Diagnosis of MS

Discovering MS in its early stages is crucial as it provides the chance to seek treatment and are prepared for what comes in the future. The medical history and neurological examination along with imaging techniques such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), lumbar punctures (LP) for cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) analysis, evoked potentials, and blood sample analysis can be used to diagnose multiple sclerosis [16].

Treatments and Management

The treatment of multiple sclerosis can be divided into disease-modifying therapies, which are typically MS-

specific, and symptomatic therapies, which are frequently used in other disease areas to treat neurological dysfunction-related symptoms. Symptomatic therapies are pharmaceutical and non-pharmaceutical therapies that target symptoms caused by CNS injury. These therapies are not MS-specific in general [17]. However, there are numerous management and treatments available to control the disease and its symptoms. Most treatments target speeding up the recovery from the attacks, managing the symptoms, and slowing down the progress of the disease. The interest in early treatment of multiple sclerosis (MS) in order to prevent long-term disability has increased as both the number of disease-modifying medicines and their effectiveness have improved. Traditionally, treatments have been immunosuppressants (such as fingolimod, natalizumab, and ocrelizumab) or immunomodulators (such as interferon beta, glatiramer acetate, and teriflunomide), which means that continual treatment is required to maintain the suppression of inflammation (and disease activity) [17]. This disease is one of the most disabling diseases that can strike people at a young age; as a result, these patients face a great deal of difficulty when it comes to their quality of life (QoL). Patients with chronic and debilitating conditions such as multiple sclerosis deal with the challenges that are associated with their disease [18]. Multiple Sclerosis (MS) exerts a substantial influence on various dimensions of patients' and families' well-being, including physical, psychological, social, and economic domains [19]. Quality of life is a wide notion influenced by various factors outside the patient's health state. These variables include the degree of autonomy, social context, and psychological condition. The evaluation of QoL has been an increasingly acknowledged part of MS research [20]. The notion of Quality of Life (QoL) and Health-Related Quality of Life (HRQOL) and their determinants have undergone a transformation since the 1980s to encompass aspects of overall QoL that have been demonstrated to have an impact on health, either physical or mental. Additional factors that are anticipated to impact Health-Related Quality of Life (HRQOL) encompass disease symptoms, adverse drug reactions, employment status, economic considerations, engagement in leisure activities, and performance of routine daily tasks [21]. HRQOL represents the connection between QoL and an individual's health status. In general, it is regarded as multidimensional, comprising physical and occupational function, emotional status, social interaction, and somatic sensations. Therefore, the purpose of HRQOL questionnaires is to give an all-encompassing, subjective measurement of the impact of the disease (including aspects of health that cannot be evaluated by observer-based measurements), the

impact of treatment, and the presence of side effects [22].

[23] state that the QoL of an MS patient becomes affected by various factors, especially considering the possible development, impact, or forced changes to the current lifestyle. Physical determinants such as physical impairment, symptomatic hindrances, upper extremity functions, and physical degradation become the most apparent determinants to consider when understanding and analyzing the QoL of MS patients. The QoL of MS patients dictates similar determinants to the previously assessed and explored factors or elements. Depression, which was more prevalent than anxiety, appears as the primary psychosocial concern for MS patients, especially considering its impact on their physiological status, mental capacities, and overall QoL [24]. The disease's physical difficulties and limitations substantially influence QoL and should be treated or rehabilitated. The inability to do routine physical acts lowers QoL and may indicate the need for physical help. MS affects sexual abilities, which must be considered in therapy. Saudi Arabian MS patients need a comprehensive analysis and treatment strategy to address all quality-of-life issues [25]. It is essential for healthcare providers to take the initiative in exploring other avenues beyond the standard therapeutic range. To reduce the impact that MS has on quality of life and ability to perform activities of daily living (ADLs), it is important to encourage healthy lifestyle patterns [26]. [27] attempted to systematically review the quality of life of adult MS patients through extensive analysis of existing clinical research. With the lack of a definitive cure in MS cases, the best method of care appears to be the improvement of the quality of life of patients, indicating the importance of understanding and developing the quality of life of MS patients. [28] recognize the importance of health-related quality-of-life improvement in MS patients. Their study also surmises the lack of psychosocial adjustments and recognition within the QoL of MS patients, including the mental toll of the disease at varying stages and in different patients.

[29] acknowledge that MS patients often have poor QoL, which impacts various aspects of their daily living and potentially worsens their condition. In addition to physical disability, emotional and psychological status, sociodemographic factors can also impact MS patients' QoL. The findings demonstrate the significance of clinical, psychosocial, and demographic factors as QoL risk and protective factors [27]. The evaluation of the patient's quality of life is one of the most essential methods for measuring the disease's impact. In addition, it aids in monitoring the clinical status of patients and determining the treatment's efficacy [30]. The quality of life (QoL) of individuals with Multiple Sclerosis (MS) can be influenced by many of disease-

related factors, such as to the level of disability or type of MS, as well as personal variables such as social support, education level, age, and employment status [31]. Indeed, previous studies have already revealed that healthcare providers and patients disagree on which health categories are most essential in MS [32]. A number of relapses, physical disability progression, and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) disease activity indicate only part of the impact that MS has on a patient's everyday life [33]. In recent decades, MS patients deemed vitality, pain, as well as general, emotional, and mental health also relevant as elements determining the HRQOL [22]. The MS nurse plays a crucial role in providing comprehension of the disease and recognizing that information needs will vary at different disease stages. Psychological stress can have a negative effect on MS; consequently, having an expert resource such as the MS nurse may enhance patient outcomes [19]. The MS nurse plays a crucial role in educating, coordinating, advocating for, and providing ongoing support to patients, families, and caregivers affected by this disease throughout their journey. Nurses are becoming prominent providers of care for people with MS [34]. In primary care settings, nurse practitioners are positioned at the front lines of identifying motor, sensory, and cognitive impairments that may aid in the diagnosis of multiple sclerosis. Patients with chronic illnesses, such as multiple sclerosis (MS), are frequently referred to a neurologist; however, they often return to the primary care setting for ongoing management. Nurse practitioners, in their diverse capacities as administrators, educators, collaborators, consultants, investigators, and advocates, possess the ability to recognize and address relapses, symptoms, and treatment-induced adverse effects that may impact the progression of the illness [35]. Nurses' role in caring for individuals with Multiple Sclerosis (MS) is paramount and is expected to undergo further development. As our comprehension of the mechanisms involved in the development and progression of this ailment deepens, there will be an increase in innovative therapeutic approaches aimed at enhancing patient outcomes. Hence, it is imperative for nurses to consistently enhance their comprehension of MS management, investigation, and optimal approaches in patient evaluation and treatment. The effective management of the challenging and complex disease of MS can be facilitated by the collaboration, expertise, and optimal access to care provided by nurses working in tandem with the MS team [36]. Nurses play a crucial role in the care of patients with multiple sclerosis (MS). They are capable of delivering a multidimensional role that encompasses various aspects of patient care. This includes providing patients with information and education about their condition at different stages of the disease, offering advice on

relapse management, and managing symptoms such as fatigue, incontinence, cognitive problems, and other conditions associated with the disease [37]. Finally, to the best of my knowledge, only a few studies have evaluated the impact of multiple sclerosis on HRQOL among those patients in Saudi Arabia. Health-related quality of life (HRQOL) evaluations in MS patients help nurses, physicians, health care providers, and researchers understand the factors, disease features, and therapy that affect patients' HRQOL. In addition, it's essential to understand how difficult it is to care for multiple sclerosis patients and how their condition impacts their activities of daily living (ADL). On the other hand, the evaluation of HRQOL can improve the satisfaction of patient's life and how they can manage it. It will be valuable as an outcome measure since it will offer a framework for assessing the changes affecting patients' HRQOL and minimizing consequences.

Materials and Methods

Study Design

A descriptive cross-sectional design was utilized in this study.

Research Setting

The study was conducted at the Prince Sultan Military Medical City in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, MS Clinic, and MS Day Case Unit. Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC) formerly known as Riyadh Military Hospital is located in Riyadh City, the capital of Saudi Arabia, considered one of the most advanced Hospitals in the Middle East. with a capacity of about +1200 beds. Services are provided to outpatients and inpatients in 23 medical and surgical specialties, the most Prominent among them are cardiology, oncology, neurology, urology, hematology, bone marrow transplantation, and others.

Sample Size

The convenience Sample of the studied population are patients in Prince Sultan Military Medical City in Riyadh, who are diagnosed with multiple sclerosis clinically and radiologically according to modified Macdonald criteria, MS patients who attended the MS clinic and MS day case at PSMMC, and who were fit for inclusion criteria.

According to the statistics provided by the Coordinator of MS patients in PSMMC, the number of patients with MS is 1350 active cases in 2022. In this formula, the confidence level was 95%. Besides, this study's margin of error (D) was 5%. The sample size was further estimated to be 300 individuals.

Inclusion Criteria

Male and female Patients older than 18 years old, who were diagnosed with MS more than 1 year. [38] acknowledge the quality of life in the first year after a diagnosis of multiple sclerosis was, on average, good and consistent. And all types of MS medication (SC, IV, and oral) will be included.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients newly diagnosed with MS.
- Patients with a history of disabilities from other diseases not related to MS.
- Patients with psychiatric disorders.

Data Collection Tool

Multiple Sclerosis Quality of Life -54 items (MSQOL-54) questionnaire, which was developed by Vickrey [39], and adapted by Alshubaili to the Arabic version of MSQOL-54 validated [40]. In this way, we used the MSQOL-54 because it was the most common and standard disease-specific questionnaire we could find to measure QoL in people with MS [41]. It's divided into two parts:

Part I: This part Consists of two sections:

Section A addressed the participants' socio-demographic characteristics that obtain the following information: (gender, age, marital status, education, and employment status).

Section B addressed the participants' illness information (age at disease onset, duration of illness, current medication, mode of administration of medication, and comorbidities).

Part II: The MSQOL-54 tool consists of a multidimensional health assessment survey questionnaire that determines QoL factors, both general and specific, to accurately and comprehensively analyze the status of an MS patient's current quality of life. A total of 54 structured closed-end questions are present in 2 categories: Physical health composite and Mental health composite which are divided into 12 subcategories, which include physical health, physical limits, emotional limits, pain, emotional well-being, energy, perceptions, social capacity, cognitive ability, distress, overall quality of life, and sexual function.

The number of questions in each category as follows:

Physical health composite consists of Physical health contained (10 structured closed-end questions), role limitation due to physical problems contained (4 structured closed-end questions), pain contained (3 structured closed-end questions), energy contained (5 structured closed-end questions), health perception contained (5 structured closed-end questions), social function contained (3 structured closed-end questions), health distress contained (4 structured closed-end questions) and sexual function contained (4 structured closed-end questions).

Mental health composite consists of health distress contained (4 structured closed-end questions), overall quality of life contained (2 question structured closed-end questions), role limitation due to emotional problems contained (3 structured closed-end questions), emotional well-being contained (5 structured closed-end questions), and cognitive

function contained (4 structured closed-end questions).

Scoring

There is no total score that can be obtained from the MSQOL-54. A weighted combination of scale scores can be used to create two summary scores: physical health composite (PHC) and mental health composite (MHC). Also, the overall Quality of life can be derived from the last 2 questions in the questionnaire.

Reliability and Validity

The MSQOL-54's 12 subscales have strong internal consistency with Cronbach's alphas from 0.75 to 0.96. These 12 subscales have strong test-retest reliability with intraclass correlation values from 0.66 to 0.96. MSQOL-54 is validated [39].

[40] reported MSQOL-54 Arabic version shows good internal consistency, with Cronbach's alphas ranging from 0.73 to 0.96, and the instrument's construct validity was determined by factor analysis.

Ethical and Legal Considerations

- Ethical approval (IRB) from Prince Sultan Medical Military City (PSMMC) ethical committee was obtained (E-2071)

- Official Permission from the Scientific Research Center (SRC) and Nursing Continuous Training and Research (NCTR) at PSMMC

- The questionnaire MSQOL-54 was attached to a Participants Information Sheet (PIS) and consent. It explained the research purpose, the possible risks, benefits, and what the participants must do if they agree to participate. Also, their rights to terminate the data at any time. PIS clearly assured that there would be no potential physical or psychological harm and no financial was provided to the participants.

Data Analysis

The statistical analysis of the data and data presentation was conducted using "Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS version-28)". However, after the questionnaire data were collected, it was coded, and inserted into the SPSS. Descriptive statistics central tendency for analyzing the socio-demographic data and QoL scores such as frequencies and percentages. Also, Correlation tests estimate the relationship between the physical and mental health composite scores as well as the overall quality of life scores Person's correlation test is used. Also, association with the socio-demographic characteristics variables such as; education level, age group, marital status, and employment status utilized by the Kurskall-Wallis test except gender were analyzed by independent T-test. While association with illness information variables such as subtypes of MS, disease duration, route of medication, and number of relapses were utilized by the Kurskall-Wallis test. A P value if less than 0.05 is considered as significant.

Results

The findings of this study were presented in three parts:

Part I:

It describes the distribution of studied MS patients according to socio-demographic characteristics (Table 1) and (Figure 3 – Figure 4). Also, the distribution of studied MS patients according to illness information (Table 2).

Part II:

This part presents the mean, SD, and range of the three categories, Physical Health Composite (PHC), Mental Health Composite (MHC), and overall quality of life (Table 3).

Part III:

This part presents the Pearson correlation between PHC, MHC and overall quality of life. In addition, the association of the studied MS patient's socio-demographic characteristics and illness information with the Physical Health Composite (PHC), Mental Health Composite (MHC), and overall quality of life. (Table 4 – Table 13).

Table 1: The Distribution of Studied MS Patients According to Their Socio-Demographic Characteristics

Characteristics	N	%
Gender		
Male	127	42.3%
Female	173	57.7%
Age group		
18-24	54	18%
25-34	133	44%
35-44	81	27%
> 44	32	11%
Marital Status		
Single	149	49.7%
Married	126	42%
Divorced	25	8.3%
Educational Level		
General Education	122	40.7%
College/University	155	51.7%
Postgraduate	23	7.7%
Employment status		
Student	42	14%
Employee	158	52.7%
Unemployed	100	33.3%

Table 1 illustrate the number and percentage of studied MS patients according to their socio-demographic characteristics. The results indicate that 57.7% of the studied MS patients were female, while 42.3% were male. Less than half of them (44%) belonged to the age group 25-34 years, and 11% of them were categorized as belonging to the age group of over 44 years. Also, 49.7% of studied MS patients were Single (49.7%), whereas 8.3% of them were divorced. Regarding the

education level, the result showed 51.7% of them had completed studies at college or university, while 8% of them were postgraduate. Moreover, 52.7% of studied MS patients were employed, while 14% of them were students in employment status.

Table 2: The distribution of studied MS patients according to their illness information

Illness information	N	%
Subtype of Multiple sclerosis		
RRMS	195	65%
SPMS	49	16.3%
PPMS	49	16.3%
PRMS	7	2.3%
Age at disease onset (in years)		
18-24	158	53%
25-34	119	40%
35-44	18	6%
>44	5	2%
Disease duration of Multiple sclerosis		
1-5 years	148	49.3%
5-10 years	82	27.3%
11 years or above.	70	23.3%
Are you using medication for Multiple sclerosis?		
Yes	286	95.3%
No	14	4.7%
If (9) yes, what is the current treatment?		
Interferon beta-1 a (Avonex)	12	4%
Interferon beta-1 a (Rebif)	28	9.3%
Interferon beta-1 b (Betaferon)	35	11.7%
Fingolimod (Gilenya)	30	10%
Dimethyl fumarate (Tecfidera)	24	8%
Teriflunomide (Aubagio)	8	2.7%
Cladribine (Mavenclad)	7	2.3%
Natalizumab (Tysabri)	70	23.3%
Ocrelizumab (Ocrevus)	29	9.7%
Rituximab (Rituxan)	43	14.3%
Not on any medication	14	4.7%
The route of medication administration		
Oral medication	70	23.3%
Injection medication (Intramuscular or Subcutaneous)	74	24.7%
Intravenous medication	142	47.3%
Not on any medication	14	4.7%
During the past 12 months, how many relapses happened?		
Only one time	79	26.3%
2 – 4 times	63	21%
5 and more	8	2.7%
No relapse happened	150	50%
Comorbidity:		
Diabetic mellitus	14	4.7%

Hypertension	7	2.3%
Thyroid disease	8	2.7%
Obesity	3	1%
Anemia	4	1.3%
Asthma	10	3.3%
Irritable bowel syndrome	2	0.7%
No comorbidity	225	75%

Table 2 shows the number and percentages of the studied MS patients according to illness information, which 195 (65%) had RRMS, while 49 (16.3%) had secondary and primary PMS for both, and only 7 (2.3%)

for Progressive-relapsing MS. More than half 53% were diagnosed between (18-24) years, while only 2% were diagnosed above 44 years. Approximately 49.3% had a duration of MS illness (1-5 years). The majority of patients (95.3%) were on treatment for multiple sclerosis, with Natalizumab (Tysabri) being the most commonly used medication (23%), followed by Rituximab (Rituxan) (14.3%). In terms of the route of medication administration, 47.3% of patients received intravenous medication. Furthermore, 50% of the respondents did not experience a relapse in the past 12 months, and 75% did not had any comorbidities.

Figure 3 Shows the distribution of studied MS patients according to the current medication.

Figure 4 Shows the distribution of studied MS patients according to the age at disease onset

Table 3 shows that the mean and SD of the categories among the studied MS patients was 69.69 ± 18.14 , and that was 56.43 ± 17.65 and 56.88 ± 22.0 respectively for the Physical Health Composite (PHC) and Mental Health Composite (MHC). The minimum and maximum scores were PHC (2.80 – 89.10), MHC (8.80 – 94.20), and overall quality of life (15 – 100). This indicates that the

studied MS patients are below the mean for each category considered as having low quality of life. Furthermore, 56.3% of studied MS patients were below the mean in PHC, 52% of them were below the mean in MHC, and 53.3% of them were below the mean in overall quality of life.

Table 3: The mean, Standard Deviation, MIN, and MAX of Categories among Studied MS Patients

Variable	Mean	SD	MIN	MAX
Physical Health Composite	56.43	17.65	2.80	89.10
Mental Health Composite	56.88	22.00	8.80	94.20
Overall quality of life	69.69	18.14	15	100

Correlation between overall quality of life and PHC and MHC.

Table 4 shows the correlation degree among PHC, MHC, and overall quality of life, the table showed that the correlation degree between Overall QoL and PHC (0.707), between Overall QoL and MHC (0.772), and PHC and MHC (0.811), and all results indicate a positive strong correlation.

Table 5 illustrates the association between Education level and PHC, MHC, and overall quality of life. It shows that there is no statistical significance relation between education and HRQOL in categories, since (p-value >0.05).

Table 6 display the association between age groups and PHC, MHC, and overall quality of life. It shows that there is statistical significance in age groups toward categories Physical Health Composite (PHC), Mental Health Composite (MHC), and Overall quality of life were significantly associated with the ages of the patients as; the younger patients (18-24 years) were significantly had the highest mean score in both PHC (65.5 ± 11.4; P = 0.00) and overall QOL (74.1 ± 15.9; P = 0.00) than other groups, while in MHC the patient (25-34) had highest mean score (61.7 ± 21.9; P = 0.00)

Table 4: Pearson Correlation Test

	Overall quality of life	Physical Health Composite	Mental Health Composite
Overall quality of life	1		
Physical Health Composite	0.707**	1	
Mental Health Composite	0.772**	0.811**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 5: The association between Categories (PHC, MHC, and overall QoL) in Studied MS Patients Regarding Educational Levels

Variable	Physical Health Composite	Mental Health Composite	Overall quality of life
Level of education	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)
General Education	54.4(19)	55.8(23.4)	68.8(21)
College/University	57.7(17.4)	56.6(21.5)	69.2(15.7)
Postgraduate	58.3(9.4)	63.3(16)	77.1(15.4)
Kruskal-Wallis H	1.90	1.95	3.71
P-value	0.387	0.376	0.156

Note: Kruskal-Wallis H test was used. *P-value is significant (< 0.05)

Table 6: The Association between Categories (PHC, MHC, and overall QoL) in Studied MS Patients Regarding Age Groups

Variable	Physical Health Composite	Mental Health Composite	Overall quality of life
age groups	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)
18-24	65.5(11.4)	61.4(20.1)	74.1(15.9)
25-34	60.1(16.8)	61.7(21.9)	73.2(18.2)
35-44	48.8(17.1)	49.5(20.3)	63.3(18.1)
>44	44.6(17.8)	47.6(22)	63.4(15.5)
Kruskal-Wallis H	50.03	24.3	20.7
P-value	0.00*	0.00*	0.00*

Note: Kruskal-Wallis H test was used. * P-value is significant (< 0.05)

Table 7 explores the association between marital status and PHC, MHC, and overall quality of life. It shows that there is statistical significance in patients' marital status toward categories, Physical Health Composite (PHC),

Mental Health Composite (MHC), and Overall quality of life was significantly associated with the marital status of the patients as; the singles patients were significantly had the highest mean score in PHC (60.1 ± 16.3; P =

0.00), MHC (59.6 ± 21.1; P = 0.011) and overall QOL (72 ± 17.9; P = 0.012) than other groups.

Table 8 illustrates the association between gender and PHC, MHC, and overall quality of life. It shows that there is statistical significance in patients' gender toward categories, Mental Health Composite (MHC), and this significance is caused by females as they had the highest mean score (57.8 ± 24.3; P = 0.002), while there is no statistical significance in Physical Health Composite (PHC) and the Overall quality of life was regarding the patient's gender.

Table 9 illustrate the association between employment status and PHC, MHC, and overall quality of life. It shows that there is statistical significance in patients' employment status toward categories, Physical Health Composite (PHC), and this significance is caused by students as they had the highest mean score (66.8 ± 12.08; P = 0.00), while there is no statistical significance in Mental Health Composite (MHC) and the Overall quality of life was regarding the employment status.

Table 7: The association between Categories (PHC, MHC, and overall QoL) in Studied MS Patients Regarding Marital Status

Variable	Physical Health Composite	Mental Health Composite	Overall quality of life
Marital status	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)
Single	60.1(16.3)	59.6(21.1)	72(17.9)
Married	55(16.7)	55.9(22.3)	69.1(17)
Divorced	40.8(20.9)	45.1(21.7)	58.6(21.3)
Kruskal-Wallis H	21.9	8.99	8.91
P-value	0.00*	0.011*	0.012*

Note: Kruskal-Wallis H test was used. * P-value is significant (< 0.05)

Table 8: The Association between Categories (PHC, MHC, and overall QoL) in Studied MS Patients Regarding Their Gender

Variable	Physical Health Composite	Mental Health Composite	Overall quality of life
Gender	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)
Male	55.2(19.2)	55.6(24.3)	70.3 (18.7)
Female	57.2(16.4)	57.8(24.3)	69.2(17.7)
P-value	0.137	0.002*	0.74

Note: Independent T-test was used. * P-value is significant (< 0.05)

Table 9: The Association between Categories (PHC, MHC, and overall QoL) in Studied MS Patients Regarding Their Employment Status

Variable	Physical Health Composite	Mental Health Composite	Overall quality of life
Employment status	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)
Student	66.8 (12.09)	63.5(23.2)	74.5 (18.5)
Employee	55.38(19.4)	56.8(24.07)	68.5 (18.4)
Unemployed	53.7(15.05)	54.1(17.11)	69.4 (17.3)
Kruskal-Wallis H	17.5	5.37	3.01
P-value	0.00*	0.068	0.222

Note: Kruskal-Wallis H test was used. * P-value is significant (< 0.05).

Table 10 explores the association between subtypes of MS and PHC, MHC, and overall quality of life. It shows that there is no statistical significance on MSQoL-54 categories, since (p-value >0.05).

Table 11 illustrate the association between MS duration and PHC, MHC, and overall quality of life. It shows that there is statistical significance on categories, since (p-

value <0.05). Physical Health Composite (PHC) is significant and the patients with MS duration (1-5 years) had the highest mean score (59.4±14.8, P = 0.00), while in both MHC & overall QoL, the patients with (5-10 years) of MS duration had the highest mean score (59.6±23, P = 0.003) & (73.3±165.7, P = 0.001) respectively.

Table 10: The Association between Categories (PHC, MHC, and overall QoL) in Studied MS Patients regarding their MS type.

Variable	Physical Health Composite	Mental Health Composite	Overall quality of life
MS subtype	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)
(RRMS)	150.63	148.52	144.55
(SPMS)	144.98	159.08	159.53
(PPMS)	162.46	153.82	159.70
(PRMS)	101.71	122.36	188.57
Kruskal-Wallis H	3.345	1.390	3.37
P-value	0.341	0.708	0.337

Note: Kruskal-Wallis H test was used. *P-value is significant (< 0.05).

Table 11: The Association between Categories (PHC, MHC, and overall QoL) in Studied MS Patients Regarding Their MS Duration

Variable	Physical Health Composite	Mental Health Composite	Overall quality of life
MS duration	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)
1-5 years	59.4(14.8)	58.9(21.1)	70.8(17.7)
5-10 years	58.5(19.2)	59.6(23)	73.3(16.7)
11 years or above.	47.4(18.4)	49.3(21.1)	62.8(18.8)
Kruskal-Wallis H	21.49	11.44	14.35
P-value	0.00*	0.003*	0.001*

Note: Kruskal-Wallis H test was used. * P-value is significant (< 0.05).

Table 12 displays the association between the Route of medication and PHC, MHC, and overall quality of life. It shows that there is statistical significance in PHC categories, where Injection medication (Intramuscular or Subcutaneous) had the highest mean score (61±17.6, P = 0.013), while there is no statistical significance relation between the route of medication, and MHC & overall QoL.

Table 13 explores the association between the number of relapses and PHC, MHC, and overall quality of life. It shows that there is statistical significance on PHC, where patients with no relapse happened to them had the highest mean score (58.5±16.3, P = 0.012), while there is no statistical significance on patients who had relapses over the past 12 months has no significant impact in MHC & overall QoL.

Table 12: The Association between Categories (PHC, MHC, and overall QoL) in Studied MS Patients Regarding Their Route of Medication

Variable	Physical Health Composite	Mental Health Composite	Overall quality of life
Route of medication	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)
Oral medication	58.1(13)	57.5(18.6)	71(16.9)
Injection medication	61(17.6)	62.7(21.8)	72.4(14.9)
Intravenous medication	53.6(19)	53.6(23.3)	67.4(20.3)
Not on any medication	51.8(17.8)	55.4(20.3)	70.9(14.1)
Kruskal-Wallis H	10.78	7.76	2.25
P-value	.013*	.051	0.521

Note: Kruskal-Wallis H test was used. *P-value is significant (< 0.05).

Table 13: The Association between Categories (PHC, MHC, and overall QoL) in Studied MS Patients Regarding Relapse that Happened to Them over the Past 12 Months

Variable	Physical Health Composite	Mental Health Composite	Overall quality of life
Relapses over past 12 months	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)
Only one time	58.2(15.6)	55.9(21.3)	70.4(16.6)
2 – 4 times	51.4(20.3)	53.7(24)	67.3(23.3)
5 and more	38.1(23.9)	44.2(24.7)	62.7(27.5)
No relapse happened	58.5(16.2)	59.3(21)	70.6(15.6)
Kruskal-Wallis H	11.02	5.57	0.195
P-value	0.012*	0.135	0.978

Note: Kruskal-Wallis H test was used. *P-value is significant (< 0.05).

Discussion

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a prevalent and incapacitating neuroinflammatory condition characterized by progressive deterioration. The disease predominantly impacts individuals in their most productive years, especially young and middle-aged adults, thereby exacerbating the already substantial economic costs associated with the illness [42]. This disease has a significant impact on various aspects of the patients' lives. As the disease advances, certain exacerbations may resolve with residual symptoms, leading individuals with multiple sclerosis (MS) to cope with an increasing number of impairments and limitations to their daily routine. As per the findings of various studies, it has been observed that the health-related quality of life in PwMS is comparatively lower than that of the general population [43].

Using the MSQOL-54 it is more specific to PwMS. In Saudi Arabia, a few studies attempted to explore the QOL in patients with multiple sclerosis such as [20] [44]. However, the two studies used generic (not MS-specific) tools to measure QOL such as EuroQOL-5 Dimensions (EQ-5D) questionnaire and 36-item Short Survey (SF-36). In addition, in this study, there was a strong correlation between categories (PHC, MHC, and overall QOL).

The focus of this study is only on those diagnosed with the condition. Results specifically showed that among the factors studied, age, marital status, gender, employment status, MS duration, route of medication, and patient relapse all have significant effects on the quality of life of the MS patient. Meanwhile, education and MS type have no such effect. Some of these findings were supported and others are not supported by the existing literature, particularly studies done on other countries and the population of the MS patients. In the present study, it was observed that the overall Quality of Life received a higher score compared to PHC and MHC. The potential reason for this difference could be attributed to the fact that Overall QOL pertains to the comprehensive assessment of the quality of life of individuals with MS, whereas PHCS and MHCS encompass questions pertaining to both physical and emotional domains. More than half of studied MS patients had lower than the mean of the PHC, MHC, and overall quality of life which indicates low quality of life. According to the result of this study, there was no statistically significant relationship between Education level and HRQOL in patients with MS. Similar findings have been reported in many studies [45]; [46]. However, this finding contrasts with previous findings from the literature, [41] reported that the highest level of education patients had higher HRQOL than less-educated patients. Furthermore, [47] reported that education seems to affect HRQOL, as patients who had

completed high school or college had higher physical health composite ratings than patients who had not completed high school or college.

The present study showed that age had a correlation with HRQOL among PwMS, which are younger patients had better scores of PHC, MHC, and overall quality of life than older. This pattern of results is consistent with the previous literature [46]; [48]; [49]; [50]. On the other hand, [45] found no relationship between age and HRQOL among PwMS.

The findings in this study showed that when compared with marital status (single, married, and divorced) PwMS, the singles attained better HRQOL in all subscales PHC, MHC, and overall Quality of life. [45] reported that unmarried patients had good scores in the domains of QOL. This finding contrasts with that of previous studies, which revealed that patients' Singles had lower HRQOL [51].

There was a significant difference in MHC scores between Females and males, which are females having a higher score in MHC, and no significant statistical differences in PHC and Overall QOL in both. [52] demonstrated that Female with MS scored higher on the QOL evaluation. The authors state that because women have better mechanisms for adjusting to adversity, difficulties have less of an impact on the evaluation of their QOL. Many studies show no significant statistical differences in PHC and MHC scores between females and males [50]; [53]; [54]; [55]. On the other hand, there was one study showed that male was associated with lower QOL [56]. Also, In another research, males scored lower than women on the physical components of QOL [57].

In the past, it was already established that MS patients benefit from work. The present study also showed that employment status has an impact on MS patients' QoL. It matches a recent study [58]. Employment increases social connection and self-worth [59]. Unemployed people have increased depression [59]; [60]; [61].

The duration of a disease is another factor that reduces the quality of life. It primarily affects physical and mental evaluations. As the disease progresses, patients become increasingly dependent on others, which diminishes their quality of life. This study revealed that MS patients with a long disease duration had lower MHC, PHC, and overall quality of life than those with a shorter illness duration. These results are consistent with, [41] reported that PwMS with Long disease duration had Poorer MHC and PHC than shorter. Also, [62]; [63]; [23] demonstrated that patients with a prolonged duration of MS reported a reduced QOL. However, in studies [64]; [65] reported no correlation between illness duration, degree of disability, and QOL assessment.

In the present study, patient relapse has a significant effect on the quality of life of the MS patient. Relapse of the disease was also observed to be a significant predictor of both PHC and MHC [57]. [66] discovered that more relapses in the previous two years were related to worse QoL. [67] discovered that patients with relapses had a lower HRQOL than those without relapses. They also discovered that delaying illness recurrence improved QoL. [68] reported a correlation between relapses and HRQoL, wherein patients with more severe relapses experienced a bigger decrease in HRQoL than those with modest relapses.

In the present study, MS types showed no relationship with HRQOL. However, research showed that MS type does not affect QOL [29]. Relapsing-remitting MS patients have a better quality of life, according to past studies as well. Literature supports this observation [23]; [69]. Progressive multiple sclerosis (MS) patients have a faster start and more severe symptoms, which may explain their poorer quality of life (QOL) [70].

This study showed that patients with injectable medication IM and SC had better HRQOL in all domains (only PHC had statistically significant). There was no correlation between MS patients' adherence to injectable medicines and their HRQOL [47]. Similar results were found in studies of QOL in younger MS patients taking interferon medications, with no effect of the medication on HRQOL [18].

Conclusion

In conclusion, the results of this study provide evidence of a strong interaction between the disease and the physical and mental categories of HRQOL in patients with MS. Also, those patients suffering from impairments in their QOL. Furthermore, health-related quality of life was significantly affected by socio-demographic factors including gender, age, marital status, and employment status, as well as by illness information such as disease duration, number of relapses, and route of medication. Also, this study showed that HRQOL in PwMS is not related to education level and subtype of MS.

Recommendation

- Conduct health education sessions that incorporate the latest evidence-based research on treatments and exercise regimens, which have demonstrated a favorable impact on the improvement of the participant's medical conditions.
- It is recommended that PwMS adhere to evidence-based guidelines aimed at mitigating the potential complications associated with this condition.
- Involving PwMS, their family members, and significant others in the development of care plans for those patients can facilitate support and encouragement towards effective management of the condition.

- It is recommended that PwMS adhere to a regimen of physiotherapy and psychotherapy sessions in order to enhance their functional capacity and overall well-being.

- It is recommended to provide comprehensive care to PwMS, healthcare providers should consider screening the quality of life in regular practice.

Limitations

Some limitations of this study require attention. The subcategories of the physical health composite (PHC) questionnaire pertain to sexual function, which had been found to be incomplete due to cultural differences in Saudi Arabia and were withdrawn. Also, all data were collected from PwMS one hospital in Riyadh; therefore, findings cannot be generalized in Saudi Arabia.

Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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